

Extraction-spectrophotometric determination of rhenium(VII) with thiocyanate and amidines in the presence of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide

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A simple and selective spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of rhenium(VII) in the ore sample based on the reaction of Re^{VII} with thiocyanate in the presence of tin(II) chloride in sulfuric acid media and subsequent extraction of the complex with chloroform solution of *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (DPBA) and its nine derivatives in the presence of a cationic surfactant, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB). The effects of acids and organic solvents on the extraction of the metal and colour intensity of the complex are discussed. The tolerance limits of diverse ions are very high. Mo^{VI} interferes it but is removed by prior precipitation by oxine effectively. The molar absorptivity and detection limit of the method with DPBA are $(3.65 \pm 0.02) \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.004 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, respectively. The relative standard deviation of the method at a level of $25 \mu\text{g Re}^{\text{VII}} / 10 \text{ ml}$ is $\pm 1.2\%$.

Classical thiocyanate method¹ for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of rhenium(VII) suffer from various experimental difficulties. Many other methods using various chromogenic organic reagents have also been reported². But the applicability of these methods is also not entirely suitable. Therefore, in this investigation, ten amidine derivatives of imidoyl chlorides are used as extractants in order to develop a highly selective and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of rhenium(VII) as quaternary complex and of these *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (DPBA) has been chosen for the detailed studies. The present method overcomes the most drawbacks of classical thiocyanate and other established methods.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the orange coloured $\text{Re}^{\text{IV}}\text{-SCN}^-\text{-CTA}^+$ complex with various amidines against the reagent blank in chloroform exhibit λ_{max} at 435 nm. Various organic solvents/extractants were tested for the extraction of $\text{Re}^{\text{IV}}\text{-SCN}^-\text{-CTA}^+\text{-DPBA}$ complex. The extracts were evaporated, digested with acids and Re^{IV} estimated by thiourea method². The solvents used showed more than 99% recovery of the metal with different molar absorptivities at λ_{max} around 435 nm as : 1-pentanol ($\epsilon = 32100$), ethyl acetate (36300), chloroform (36500) and benzene ($29500 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). 1-Pentanol and ethyl acetate

are solvating solvent and not diluent. In carbon tetrachloride and toluene, the complex showed no extraction. Due to maximum sensitivity and selectivity, therefore, chloroform was used.

The quantitative extraction of the metal was found to be suppressed by chloride ions due to the formation of a different complex. Hence, hydrochloric acid could not be used. The optimum acidity range for complete extraction of the complex lies in the range $4.5\text{--}6.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$.

An extraction time of 2 min was sufficient for complete extraction of the complex. Following concentrations of DPBA, KSCN, tin(II) chloride and CTAB were found suitable in the ranges $(0.6\text{--}2.8) \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ in organic phase, $0.07\text{--}0.3 \text{ M}$, $0.007\text{--}0.05 \text{ M}$ and $(4.0\text{--}13.0) \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ in aqueous phase, respectively, for complete extraction and maximum colour development of the complex. Complete extraction of the complex, which remained stable for at least 4 h, was observed over the temperature range $20\text{--}40^\circ$. Variation in organic to aqueous phase ratio between 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 had no adverse effect on the complex properties.

The molar absorptivity of the complex formed with *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (DPBA) and its ten derivatives lie in the range $(2.68\text{--}3.65) \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 1). The limit of detection of the method with DPBA, the most sensitive reagent, is $0.004 \mu\text{g Re/ml}$. A linear relationship between absorbance and rhenium concentration over

Note

1.0–3.5 ppm Re was obtained with a relative standard deviation of $\pm 1.2\%$ for 25 μg Re/10 ml ($n = 10$).

Table 1. Spectral data of $\text{Re}^{\text{IV}}\text{-SCN}^- \text{-CTA}^+$ complex with various amidines, in chloroform

Amidine $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C=N-C}_6\text{H}_5$ R-N-H R	λ_{max} nm	Molar absorptivity, ϵ $\text{dm}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$
C_6H_5	435	36500	0.051
2,5-(CH_3) ₂ - C_6H_3	435	30500	0.061
2-Cl- C_6H_4	435	31300	0.060
3-Cl- C_6H_4	435	32800	0.056
4-Cl- C_6H_4	435	33500	0.055
2,5-(Cl) ₂ - C_6H_3	435	26800	0.069
2- CH_3 - C_6H_4	435	32450	0.057
3- CH_3 - C_6H_4	435	33600	0.055
4- CH_3 - C_6H_4	435	34600	0.054
$\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_7$	435	28800	0.065

The composition of the extracted complex was evaluated by curve-fitting method by plotting $\log D$ [$D = A_{\text{eq}}/(A_{\text{max}} - A_{\text{eq}})$] vs $\log [\text{SCN}^-]/\log [\text{DPBA}]/\log [\text{CTAB}]$. The result indicates the formation of a 1 : 4 : 1 : 1 ion-association complex, extractable in chloroform, of Re^{IV} : SCN^- : CTA^+ : DPBA .

The effect of ions co-existing with 25 μg Re was examined as described in the procedure and the tolerance limit of the diverse ions are as under (tolerance limits shown in perentesis are in mg) : Cr^{III} , Ni^{II} (50); tartarate, nitrate (40); Ca^{II} (20); Mg^{II} (18); Ag^{I} , Be^{II} , Ti^{IV} (15), oxalate, EDTA (12); Zr^{IV} (10); Sr^{II} (6.0); Th^{IV} (5.0); Ta^{V} , V^{V} (3.5); Nb^{V} (3.0) fluoride, sulfate, iodide (2.0); Hg^{II} , Al^{III} , Ir^{III} (1.5); Cu^{II} (0.8); La^{III} (0.6); and Mo^{VI} (0.2 mg). The possible interference of Mo could be removed by prior precipitation with oxine.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss-Jena Spekol spectrophotometer equipped with matched 1-cm silica and quartz cells was used.

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. A stock solution of rhenium(vii) was prepared by dissolving potassium per-rhenate (1.0 g) in double-distilled water and the metal content determined spectrophotometrically by thiourea method². Amidines were synthesized by condensation of an equimolar ratio of *N*-phenylbenzimidoyl chloride with appropriate amine. The resulting hydrochloride was treated with dilute ammonia in order to liberate the corresponding free base, crystallized from dilute ethanol (60%, v/v)³. A 0.26 M tin(II) chloride, 2.06 M potassium thiocyanate, 0.01 M cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and 10 M H_2SO_4 were used. A $\approx 7.35 \times 10^{-3}$ M (0.2%, w/v) solution of amidine in chloroform was employed.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the solution containing 25 μg Re^{VII} , was added solutions of tin(II) chloride (0.5 ml), potassium thiocyanate (0.5 ml) and CTAB (1 ml) Then H_2SO_4 was added and the volume made up to 10 ml with water. The aqueous phase was extracted with amidine solution (5 ml, 2 min). The extracted phase was dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate (2 g). The aqueous phase was further extracted with fresh chloroform (2×2 ml). The combined organic extracts was dried and made up to 10 ml with fresh chloroform and its absorbance measured against reagent blank.

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